

BLAST PERFORMANCE OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich composite materials possess low radar signatures, high strength-to-weight ratios and tailorable mechanical properties, but their blast resistance is not well understood. This paper presents the results of full scale air blast tests performed on a graded density foam core sandwich panel, to determine if the use of a graded core can be used to mitigate blast damage. The results are obtained using high speed 3D digital image correlation, and post-blast damage assessment. It was found that back face-sheet damage could be prevented by using a graded sandwich panel as there is less cracking towards the back of the panel, and the epoxy between the foam layers impedes crack propagation through the foam, resulting in less overall damage. The second part of this paper presents findings from a study performed using the UNDEX simulation tool in Abaqus to model the fluid-structure-interaction in underwater blast scenarios. These results were verified with full scale underwater blast testing performed in Norway in 1988 in connection with the development of a series of mine counter-measure vessels for the Royal Norwegian Navy. Using this method it was possible to successfully model cavitation development and closure in front of the tested sandwich structure, and strong agreement was found from electrical strain gauges placed on the front face-sheet of the sandwich panels in the underwater blast test experiments.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymeric foam core sandwich composites possess high strength-to-weight ratios, low radar signatures and tailorable mechanical properties, which make them attractive material choices in naval applications. In order to ascertain their suitability for these applications, it is important that they are tested in both air, and underwater blast situations. This paper presents findings from full scale air blast tests on sandwich composites, considering the use of a graded density polymeric foam core, for blast damage mitigation. The graded sandwich panel was subjected to a 100 kg TNT equivalent charge at a 15 m stand-off distance. Wang and Shukla [1] performed blast testing on sandwich panels with a graded density core, with high pressure loading, and found that the blast wave was attenuated by the lower density foam layers at the front. In the research presented in the current paper the peak pressures were not sufficient to cause core crushing, so all damage was due to the impulsive bending of the

sandwich panel. The damage caused by blast loading was determined analytically by Andrews and Moussa [2] where the deflection of the sandwich panel under static load was determined, and using a correction factor based on natural frequency the deflection under blast loading found. This method was used to predict the core cracking, debonding and front face-sheet cracking observed in the experiments presented in this paper. Hoo Fatt and Palla [3] also developed an analytical solution for the response of circular sandwich panels to blast loading, including damage predictions.

This paper also presents finite element results of far field underwater blast experiments and the fluid-structure-interaction capabilities of the UNDEX simulation tool in ABAQUS using acoustic elements to model the water. The simulations are then validated against full scale tests performed in Norway in 1988 in connection with the development of a series of mine counter-measure vessels for the Royal Norwegian Navy. Underwater impulsive loading has also been performed by Latourte et al [4] in which core crushing due to high peak pressures was present, but the low impulse lead to small amounts of bending and thus less core cracking. Full scale air and underwater blast tests have also been performed by Arora, Hooper and Dear [5, 6], considering small and large charge sizes on polymeric sandwich panels with both glass fibre and carbon fibre face-sheets.

2 AIR BLAST TESTS

2.1 Materials

Full scale air blast tests were performed on two sandwich composite structures, one with a graded density foam core, and one with a single density foam core. Both foam cores used a styrene acrylonitrile polymer, and the constructions are shown in Figure 1a for the graded density core, and Figure 1b for the single density core. Both sandwich panels had face-sheets constructed of QE1200 glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) infused with Ampreg 22 epoxy resin. The test panels were produced using vacuum consolidation, where the glass fibres and foam cores were coated in resin, before being assembled and cured under vacuum.

2.2 Test Setup

The full scale air blast tests were performed at a DNV GL test site at RAF Spadeadam, Carlisle, UK. A 100 kg Nitromethane charge was used, which had a TNT equivalence of 100 kg, and this was situated at a distance of 15 m from the test panel. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the test layout. The test panels were bolted into a steel fronted cubicle, as shown in Figure 3, with steel tubes used to prevent the core crushing when tightening the bolts. This clamping arrangement provided quasi-built-in boundary conditions. In order to track the out-of-plane displacement and back face-sheet strain of the sandwich panel during the blast, pairs of high speed cameras were situated inside the test cubicle, and 3D digital image correlation (DIC) used to calculate these parameters.

2.3 Results

This section presents the out-of-plane displacement and maximum principal strain measured during blast testing with 3D DIC. The DIC results of the graded density foam core are shown in Figure 4, with the contour plots of out-of-plane displacement and maximum principal strain shown in Figure 4a. Figure 4b shows how the central deflection of the sandwich panel changes over time, as well as the measured and predicted reflected overpressure, which show close agreement. Figure 4c shows the displacement of the centre horizontal section of the graded sandwich panel, and Figure 4d shows the rebound phase, after it has reached maximum out-of-plane displacement. These two plots are shown for the vertical central displacement in Figure 4e and Figure 4f respectively. The DIC results for the single density, 40 mm thick M100 foam core sandwich panel are presented in Figure 5, with the DIC contour plots of out-of-plane displacement and maximum principal strain shown in Figure 5a. Figure 5b provides the central displacement plot of the sandwich panel, also showing the predicted and measured reflected blast overpressure. Figure 5c shows the initial horizontal centre displacement of the panel, and Figure 5d shows the rebound of the centre section. The initial displacement and rebound of the vertical centre section are shown in Figure 5e and Figure 5f respectively. It was also shown, through post-blast sectioning of the sandwich panels, that there was less damage present in the graded

density sandwich panel, as opposed to the single density panel, as a result of the interfaces between the cores impeding crack propagation.

Figure 1: Layup schematic for a) the graded density core sandwich panel; and b) the single density core sandwich panel.

Figure 2: Schematic of the test pad layout.

Figure 3: Clamping arrangement of the sandwich panels during blast testing.

Figure 4: DIC results of the graded density core sandwich panel showing a) contour plots of out-of-plane displacement and maximum principal strain; b) the central deflection of the sandwich panel over time, alongside the predicted and measured reflected blast overpressure; c) the horizontal centre section plots for the initial deflection; d) the horizontal centre section plots for rebound; e) the vertical centre section plots for the initial deflection; and f) the vertical centre section plots for rebound.

Figure 5: DIC results of the single density M100 core sandwich panel showing a) contour plots of out-of-plane displacement and maximum principal strain; b) the central deflection of the sandwich panel over time, alongside the predicted and measured reflected blast overpressure; c) the horizontal centre section plots for the initial deflection; d) the horizontal centre section plots for rebound; e) the vertical centre section plots for the initial deflection; and f) the vertical centre section plots for rebound.

2.4 Discussion

The test results presented in this section show the response of a graded density foam core sandwich panel compared to a single density foam core sandwich panel. Figure 4 shows the 3D DIC results of the graded density sandwich panel, and it can be seen that the displacement plots of the graded core are much smoother, due to the lower density foam layers cracking more, causing less damage in the high density core at the back. From using high speed cameras with rates of 7000 frames/s and 5400 frames/s for the graded and single density core panels respectively, a deceleration is visible in the rebound, when the unloading wave reaches the damaged sections of the panels. These damaged sections are highlighted by bends in the displacement profiles. Finally, by using elastic finite element analysis (FEA), it was discovered that the use of a graded density foam core compared to an equivalent thickness sandwich panel results in equivalent out-of-plane displacement, so with the reduced though thickness cracking found due to foam layer boundaries in the graded core, it is concluded that the deflection of the graded core panel will be reduced.

3. FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF FAR FIELD UNDERWATER EXPLOSIONS

3.1 Sandwich panels used in this study

The response of sandwich panels to underwater blast is of great importance for the design of naval vessels. Whilst experimental investigations are important to determine their behaviour, they require significant financial and labour resources. Finite element analysis (FEA) has the potential of reducing the requirement for full scale field tests and, if relatively simple analysis techniques are developed, can be easily incorporated in the design process. As part of the development of such simple analysis techniques, in this project the response of a GFRP sandwich panel to a far field underwater explosion was modelled. Validation of the model was performed using newly available data from a series of instrumented, full-scale panel tests performed in Norway in 1988 in connection with the development of a series of mine counter-measure vessels for the Royal Norwegian Navy. Early attempts at modelling the response [7] led to the realisation that the fluid-structure interaction and cavitation conditions experienced by sandwich panels with compliant cores were unlike those for metal plates and single-skin laminates. These observations were later confirmed by Mäkinen [8].

Data from two similar tests were used to validate the current model results. In both cases the experimental samples were rectangular panels with a total surface of 1.9 x 1.8 m. The panel edges were clamped between steel strips and 150 mm wide flanges welded to a rectangular, steel box, giving an unsupported panel area of 1.6 x 1.5 m. The box was air-filled, thereby simulating the conditions of a ship hull. The approximate geometry of this arrangement is shown in Figure 6b. Each face sheet laminate consisted of one layer of 300 g/m² chopped strand mat (CSM), two layers of 800 g/m² woven fibres with an additional 300 g/m² CSM and a final 300 g/m² CSM layer. The matrix was iso-polyester Norpol 72-80, and the fibre weight fraction was approximately 50%. The total thickness of each face sheet was approximately 3.5 mm. A Divinycell H200 closed cell polymer foam core was used. Its thickness was 60 mm, giving a total panel thickness of 67 mm.

The blast pressures were generated with 14 kg of TNT at 30 m stand-off distance. This relatively low blast level was chosen in order to validate the modelling method without involving the need for implementing accurate material failure and degradation laws. The two panels were extensively instrumented with strain gauges both on the face laminates and inside the foam core. In both tests one of the strain gauges recorded vertical strains at the centre of the panel on the face exposed to the water. Additionally, in the first test a further gauge recorded vertical strains at the panel centre on the air side. The water pressure history was also recorded with a gauge located 920 mm in front of the panels.

3.2 FEA model

The FEA model was built using ABAQUS 6.9 [9]. A quarter model of the panel with appropriate symmetry boundary conditions was used. The core was modelled using 3D hexahedral stress elements with reduced integration and hourglass control. An element size of 10 mm was used.

Quadrilateral 2D stress elements with reduced integration and hourglass control were used for the skins and for the steel box components. Again, 10 mm elements were used. This guaranteed that the meshes in the skins and core matched to simplify the tie interface.

The water was modelled separately using tetrahedral acoustic elements. These elements have a pressure degree of freedom and are therefore able to model the blast wave propagation. Additionally, cavitation can be simulated by setting a minimum pressure the medium can sustain. However the fluid structure interactions in the model were limited to the early acoustic phase of the shock loading, corresponding to the “early time” solution for a thin plate presented by Keil [10] and others.

Figure 6: Images of the FEA model. Showing a) the acoustic mesh around the box structure; and b) the sample panel and the metal frame providing the key dimensions of the sample.

For simplicity, the H200 foam core was modelled with an isotropic, linear elastic material. The assumed Young's modulus was 250 MPa and the Poisson's ratio was 0.39.

Each face laminate was modelled as a single layer shell. A laminar anisotropic elastic model was used, as this would be necessary to include damage models in potential later models. However, the same overall properties were applied in both directions. The parameters for these models were obtained through tests performed on the same material type used for the panel manufacture. The Young's modulus and the shear modulus were assumed to be 14.6 GPa and 2.8 GPa respectively, whilst the Poisson's ratio used was 0.17. The steel box was modelled with a linear elastic material. The assumed density was 7800 kg/m³, the Young's modulus 2.1x10⁵ MPa and the Poisson's ratio 0.3.

The density of the sea water was assumed to be 1025 kg/m³ and the bulk modulus to be 2.1404x10³ MPa, whilst the cavitation limit was assumed to be -75 kPa (tension).

The inbuilt underwater blast simulation tool in ABAQUS was employed to simulate the blast pressure waves. The tool uses equations derived by Geers and Hunter [11] to simulate both the initial shock wave and the dynamics of the gas bubble created at the charge location. In this case the bubble pulses were neglected due to the large charge distance, and the analysis was confined to the effects of the initial shock wave. The software required the input of similitude parameters for the explosive used as well as the physical characteristics of the blast, including its position and the quantity of explosive material. The relevant parameters were obtained from Geers and Hunter [11], based on 1.52 g/cm³ TNT.

3.3 Results

The results from the FEA models were compared to the strain and pressure histories recorded during the blast tests.

The FEA pressure results were extracted at a location the same distance away from the simulated panel as the pressure gauge. The maximum simulated pressure was 2.75 MPa, compared to recorded values of 3 MPa in both tests. Whilst the simulated peak is lower than the measured data by approximately 10%, the FEA pressure rise time was longer, with a smoother rise and peak. The impulse recorded in the experimental tests was approximately 800 Pa s in the first millisecond, shortly after which the reflected wave from the target reached the sensor and the recorded signals became

chaotic. The FEA impulse in the same time period was 1050 Pa s.

These simulated pressures were transferred to the panels and caused significant deformations. The strains at the centre of the panel on the water side and on the air side were compared, as shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8. The FEA results for the water side strains matched closely the experimental data until about 15 ms. The air side data matched the experimental results up to the first peak at about 6 ms. Following this the results diverge, with the strains decreasing less rapidly in the numerical analysis data.

Figure 7: Water side vertical strains. The FEA results are compared to both sets of experimental data.

Figure 8: Air side vertical strains. The FEA results are compared to the results from Test 2.

3.4 Discussion

The results of the FEA show that the initial deformation peaks and, with some limitations, the following behaviour of the system can be modelled with relatively straightforward numerical techniques. The UNDEX simulation option of ABAQUS proved to be able to approximately replicate the peak of the pressure pulse, though the numerical result is lower than the measured value. However, the rise time of the pressure was too long, which affected the impulse and the pulse shape. This may have changed the basic conditions regulating the cavitation of the medium. Whilst this introduces some inaccuracy in the model, the strain results obtained indicate that the system might be relatively insensitive to this in the simulation. The simulation showed the formation and eventual closure of a cavitation bubble approximately 150 mm ahead of the target panel. This agrees with numerical predictions by Hayman [7] using simple one-dimensional plane wave propagation theory. The water side strain results show the best agreement with the experimental data. The acoustic mesh is able to model the sudden force transmitted to the panel at 6 ms, probably due to cavitation closure near the target surface. The post peak behaviour is also well matched until the later part of the simulation. The air side results are similar to experimental records until the first peak, after which the numerical results show a much larger period in their decay. This suggests that the “early time” acoustic model with cavitation is able to predict the maximum panel deformations and stresses, but effects due to the fluid flows around the target need to be taken into account at later times. This would require instead a full computational fluid dynamics model. Some differences between the predicted and measured responses may also be due to inaccuracies in the model of the box, which had to be simplified in the simulation. Additionally, the air medium was not included in this model. This could have altered the strain decay mechanism, eliminating a restraint to the panel movement.

Further work will be conducted to both improve the accuracy of the results and to expand these to more severe blast levels, for which it will be necessary to model damage to the panel.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has highlighted air blast testing performed on two sandwich panels, one with a graded density foam core and one with a single density foam core. It was concluded that the use of a graded density core, when subjected to blast loading with a peak pressure less than that of the crushable yield strength of the foam, was to reduce damage in the sandwich panel by mitigating crack propagation through the foam layer boundaries. It was also found that by increasing the crack density near the front of the panel, in the weaker, lower density foam, and reducing it in the back, higher density foam, the deflection of the back face-sheet is smoother. By creating a more smooth profile of displacement on the back face, it is implied that with higher intensity blast loading the back face of the sandwich panel will be able to withstand a greater load. The second part of this paper presented results of finite element modelling of far field underwater experiments. It was found that by using the UNDEX simulation option in Abaqus, it is possible to successfully model cavitation development and closure in front of the tested sandwich structure. The finite element model has been successfully validated against strain gauge data from full scale underwater blast tests performed on PVC core sandwich composites, with the best results being for the waterside of the composite panel, which is in contact with an acoustic mesh, representing the water.

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REFERENCES

- [1] N. Gardner, E. Wang, A. Shukla, Performance of functionally graded sandwich composite beams under shock wave loading. *Composite Structures* 94(5), 1755 (2012).
DOI: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2011.12.006.
- [2] E. Andrews, N. Moussa, Failure mode maps for composite sandwich panels subjected to air blast loading. *International Journal of Impact Engineering* 36(3), 418 (2009).
DOI 10.1016/j.ijimpeng.2008.08.005.
- [3] M. S. Hoo Fatt, L. Palla, Analytical Modelling of Composite Sandwich Panels under Blast Loads. *Journal of Sandwich Structures and Materials* 11(4), 357 (2009).
DOI 10.1177/1099636209104515.
- [4] F. Latourte, D. Grégoire, D. Zenkert, X. Wei, H.D. Espinosa, Failure mechanisms in composite panels subjected to underwater impulsive loads. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 59(8), 1623 (2011).
DOI 10.1016/j.jmps.2011.04.013.
- [5] H. Arora, P.A. Hooper, J. Dear, Dynamic response of full-scale sandwich composite structures subject to air-blast loading *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 42(11), 1651 (2011).
DOI 10.1016/j.compositesa.2011.07.018.
- [6] H. Arora, P.A. Hooper, J.P. Dear, The Effects of Air and Underwater Blast on Composite Sandwich Panels and Tubular Laminate Structures. *Experimental Mechanics* 52(1), 59 (2011).
DOI 10.1007/s11340-011-9506-z.
- [7] Hayman B. Underwater explosion loading on foam-cored sandwich panels. *Sandwich Construction 3*, EMAS, Procedures of the Third International Conference on Sandwich Construction, vol. 3, Southampton, UK: EMAS Publishing, UK; 1995.
- [8] Mäkinen K. The transverse response of sandwich panels to an underwater shock wave. *Journal of Fluids Structures* 1999;13:631–46.
DOI:10.1006/jfls.1999.0222.
- [9] Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp. *Abaqus analysis manual v6.9*. Providence, RI: 2009.
- [10] Keil AH. The response of ships to underwater explosions. Society of Naval Architects and Marine Engineers Annual Meeting, New York, Nov. 16-17 1961, available as document AD 268905, Armed Services Technical Information Agency, Arlington 12, Virginia, USA.
- [11] Geers TL, Hunter KS. An integrated wave-effects model for an underwater explosion bubble. *Journal of Acoustical Society America* 2002;111:1584–601. doi:10.1121/1.1458590.